

Effect of root pruning at various times during ripening on IR58 grain yield and its components. IRRI, 1989.

Treatment	Time of treatment (DAH) ^a	Grain yield			Filled grains (%)	Grain weight (mg)
		Actual (g/m ²)	sd ^b	Corrected ^c (g/m ²)		
Control (Jul planting)		337	29	337	64	18.7
Roots pruned	-5	190	21	217	47	16.6
	0	290	15	273	56	17.3
	5	350	40	306	62	17.5
	10	320	22	324	64	18.0
Control (Aug planting)		426	31	426	71	21.3
Roots pruned	-5	355	25	334	62	19.1
	0	350	31	389	66	20.9
	5	380	19	408	71	20.4
	10	406	48	364	67	19.3
	15	385	35	398	71	19.9

^a Days after heading. ^b Standard deviation. ^c Corrected yield assuming spikelet number is the same as in the control plot.

leaves to curl slightly the next day. Little wilting, however, was observed on the second day after pruning and none after that.

Both grain weight and ripening percentage decreased in all the treated plots (see table). The reduction in ripening percentage was higher when roots were pruned earlier, the time during which fertilization and initial grain growth occur—and when plants are most sensitive to water imbalance.

Grain yield was reduced markedly when treated before heading and by about 10% when plants were treated at 5 d after heading and later, despite the complete removal of roots (see figure). Active nutrient uptake and the supply of cytokinins from the roots might have been reduced completely because the roots and root zone were removed. Few new roots formed in the pruned plants.

Neither the nutrient uptake nor the supply of plant hormones from the roots

Effect of root pruning on grain yield of IR58. IRRI, 1989.

at this growth stage seem to be the major factor for grain filling. The principal contribution of roots to ripening is to supply sufficient water and to support the top of the plant. Grain yield was not so high in the wet weason, so the required nutrients after heading may have been smaller. Similar experiments during the dry season, when yields are higher, would help further elucidate the contribution of roots to grain filling in rice. ■

Mineral elements in Australian brown rice

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Ninety samples of brown rice from popular cultivar Amaroo were collected from commercial crops in the irrigated rice-growing regions of southern Australia at the end of the 1991-92 season. The samples were analyzed for total N using the Kjeldahl technique and for P, K, Mg, S, Ca, Mn, Na, Al, Zn, Fe, Cu, and Mo using inductively coupled plasma emission spectroscopy.

The range and mean concentrations of each element were summarized from this study and ranges reported in 22 previous studies from Southeast Asia and the USA (Table 1). Many samples in earlier studies were from crops grown under experimental conditions with various nutrient inputs. Mean concentrations of

Table 1. Comparison of elemental composition of brown rice from Australia and that reported in previous studies (all values on oven-dry weight basis).

Element	Australian crops (mean)	Range	
		This study	Previous studies ^a
		(g/kg)	
Nitrogen	13.7	11.0 - 17.0	na
Phosphorus	3.4	2.8 - 3.6	2.0 - 5.0
Potassium	2.8	2.4 - 3.5	0.7 - 3.3
Magnesium	1.3	1.2 - 1.5	0.2 - 1.7
Sulfur	1.1	0.9 - 1.3	0.3 - 2.2
Calcium	0.1	0.03 - 0.13	0.1 - 0.6
		(mg/kg)	
Manganese	48	29 - 70	2.3 - 42
Sodium	23	0 - 221	20 - 395
Zinc	19	15 - 24	7 - 33
Iron	15	6 - 78	2.3 - 60
Aluminum	15	0.6 - 42	0.3 - 30
Copper	5	1.6 - 15	1.2 - 7
Molybdenum	0.8	0 - 2	0.3 - 1.2

^a Based on data from 22 independent studies in Southeast Asia and the USA.

all mineral nutrients in Australian grain fell into the ranges found in earlier studies, except for Mn, which was generally at higher concentrations, and Ca, which was at lower concentrations. Some samples had higher Fe, Al, and Cu

concentrations than reported for samples from Southeast Asia and the USA, but some of these may have been contaminated by these elements during grinding. Grain in the previous studies also had a greater range of P and Na concentrations.

Elements removed by brown rice grain were compared with the concentrations removed by hulls and straw and the resulting nutrient harvest index (Table 2). In an average 10 t/ha crop of Amaro at 14% moisture, brown grain removed 103 kg N; straw, 61 kg N; and hulls, 3.7 kg N. Brown rice removed most of the P (25 kg in an average 10 t/ha rice crop), while straw removed 4.8 kg and hulls removed 0.4 kg, giving a nutrient harvest index of 83%. The amounts of K, Mg, Ca, Zn, and Mo removed by straw exceeded those removed by brown rice; hulls contained low concentrations. The proportion of Mn, Fe, Na, and Al removed by grain was lower than or equal to that removed by hulls, with straw removing the greatest proportion. Straw and grain removed similar amounts of Cu and S, with much lower concentrations in hulls.

At the rice mill, hulls are separated from the grain, and most are dumped and burned or converted to livestock feed. Rice straw is usually burned after harvest.

N, P, and S are the dominant fertilizer inputs for rice in southern NSW. Incorporating residues would enhance the recycling rate of all the nutrients studied. However, P would be supplied in relatively small amounts because it is predominantly exported in the brown grain. ■

Table 2. Partitioning of mineral elements by an average Amaro rice crop yielding 10 t/ha (at 14% moisture).^a

Element	Element removed			Total nutrients removed	Nutrient harvest index (%) ^b
	In brown grain	In hulls	In straw		
			(kg/ha)		
Nitrogen	103	3.7	61	167.7	61
Phosphorus	25	0.4	4.8	30.2	83
Potassium	21	9.0	212	242.0	9
Magnesium	10	0.6	14	24.6	41
Sulfur	8	0.4	5.8	14.2	56
Calcium	0.9	1.4	23	25.3	4
Manganese	0.4	0.6	5.8	6.8	6
Sodium	0.2	0.3	27	27.5	1
Aluminum	0.1	0.1	6.2	6.4	2
Iron	0.1	0.1	2.2	2.4	4
			(g/ha)		
Zinc	140	26	259	425	33
Copper	35	2	35	72	49
Molybdenum	6.0	1.4	25	32.4	19

^aA rice crop yielding 10 t/ha (at 14% moisture) will have an average of 8.4 t grain/ha, 1.6 t hulls/ha, and 11 t straw/ha. The data were calculated using concentrations of minerals on an oven-dry weight basis and multiplying by 7.5, for grain, 1.4 for hulls, and 9.6 for straw (i.e., yields at 0% moisture).

^b Nutrient harvest index = $100 \times \frac{\text{Amount in grain}}{\text{Amount in grain, hulls, and straw}}$

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Fertilizer management

Effects of *Sesbania rostrata* population, time of harvest, and urea application rate on lowland rice production

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We studied the effects of plant population and time of harvest of *Sesbania rostrata* and urea application rate on lowland rice production.

Soil was silty clay with a pH of 5.7, 0.16% N, 2.34% organic C, 16.76% ppm P, C-N ratio of 14.62, and 0.48 meq K/100 g.

The experiment was laid out in a split plot design with three replications during 1991-92 wet season (Oct-Mar). The main plot treatment was *S. rostrata* population at two levels: 62,500 and 125,000 plants/ha. *S. rostrata* harvest time was the treatment in the subplot (45 and 60 days after sowing [DAS]),

Table 1. Effect of plant population and time of harvest on N concentration (%) in plant tissue of *S. rostrata*. Maros, Indonesia.

Time of harvest (DAS)	Plant population/ha ^a	
	62,500	125,000
45	2.45 a	1.88 b
60	1.47 c	1.86 b

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significant at the 5% level by DMRT.

and levels of urea application (0, 23, and 46 kg N/ha) were the sub-subplot treatments.

S. rostrata seeds were sown in the plot and thinned based on the plant population treatment. *S. rostrata* was plowed under in preparation for rice planting according to the treatments. Rice cultivar Cisadane was planted a week later. Half of the urea was applied at planting and the rest at panicle initiation. All of the plots were also treated at planting with triple superphosphate at 26.4 kg P/ha and KCl at 41.5 kg K/ha.

Table 2. Effect of *S. rostrata* plant population, time of harvest, and rate of urea application on rice panicle number, unfilled grains, and grain yield. Maros, Indonesia.

Treatment	Panicles/hill (no.)	Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>S. rostrata</i> population/ha			
62,500	122.47 a	15.95 a	5.3 a
125,000	128.61 a	14.47 a	5.6 a
Time of harvest of <i>S. rostrata</i> (DAS)			
45	128.70 a	14.56 a	5.4 a
60	122.38 a	15.86 a	5.5 a
Rate of urea application (kg N/ha)			
0	115.32 b	17.08 a	4.4 c
23	126.62 a	15.49 b	5.7 b
46	134.68 a	13.06 c	6.4 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significant at the 5% level by DMRT.

The greatest N content in *S. rostrata* plant tissue occurred with 62,500 plants/ha and harvest at 45 DAS (Table 1).